

Metal fibres and their potential for use in composite materials – an overview

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a feasibility study on the use of metal fibres as a third component in composite materials. Briefly outlined are previous studies and investigations into metal fibres that have been used as a major constituent in a composite system and the properties that have been gained from them. Although studies into metal fibres as a third component have been uncommon, the conclusions made from past research has given an idea of the kind of property behaviour one might expect during testing of these high-potential new composite systems.

KEYWORDS: metal fibres, electromagnetic shielding, fibre/matrix adhesion, electrical and mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

In current design and manufacturing of lightweight composite structures the designer is not only designing the shape and functionalities of the structure but also the mechanical behaviour or response to mechanical loads within an envelope of sufficient resistance to temperatures, chemical and physical degradation. The structural design nowadays is limited to mechanical and environmental loading and the design envelope needs an extension to parameters with respect to tuneable electric and magnetic properties, thermal conduction, thermal expansion behaviour and ductility when appropriate. The contemporary families of organic and inorganic fibres do not offer these possibilities unless they are mingled with metallic fibres. When metal fibres that are selected with respect to mechanical and physical properties become available, a new range of materials and structural design possibilities come into play. By mingling fibres or commingling bundles of fibres (yarns) of different but compatible nature, we extend the possibilities to alloy metals and to blend polymers on a micro scale with the composition of material properties and material behaviour on a macro scale. Even plasticity and ductility can be introduced in composite materials and structures where necessary.

Metal fibres are thin filaments with diameters between 1-80µm and, like other reinforcement fibres, are rarely used individually. However, when used in bundles or as woven fabric, the sum of the whole can be greater than the parts and such is the result of the properties. Metal woven fabric, for example, has the benefit of being lighter and more 'drapeable' than its sheet metal counterpart, whilst retaining its ductility. Twisted steel fibres can be up to 11 times

stronger in tension than a typical steel plate and far more mouldable. Feasibility studies on the use of metal fibres in composites have mainly focused on use for electromagnetic shielding. Rarely has a study been performed where the continuous metal fibre is the third mechanical component in a composite. In addition, studies on the use of metal fibres in composites have also been uncommon and a probable reason for this is that the availability of such fibres in the past has been scarce. Therefore, the inclusion of metal fibres into existing composite systems has yet to be realised.

METAL FIBRE PRODUCTION

Three methods are regularly employed to produce metal fibres by various commercial manufacturers, and this section describes those utilised to produce continuous fibres. The first is wire bundle drawing in which a rod of ductile metal is made to undergo a series of drawing and annealing steps, diagrammatically shown in Figure 1(a). Once a diameter of 1mm has been reached, the wire is plated and a number of wires are combined into a large bundle and clad with iron, which are then in turn drawn and annealed to the desired diameter. The metal bundles are then leached to dissolve the iron cladding, releasing the individual metal fibres.

Secondly, melt extraction is a process in which the surface of a molten metal pool is touched by a quickly rotating water-cooled wheel [2]. The molten metal is drawn out of the pool through adhesion and partial wetting of the wheel surface and is rapidly cooled upon touching the wheel. Unless carefully controlled, the wheel can induce turbulence on the pool surface resulting in process control difficulties and consequently affects the surface properties of the fibres [3]. This method is suitable for lower melt-temperature metals.

The final method commonly used is a metal shaving process [1]. Metal fibres are produced by shaving off the edge of a coil of thin metal foil, which is rotated about its central axis. The fibres, which generally have a rougher surface, are then collected into bundles.

One other method exists that has been demonstrated to produce fibre diameters in the range of 1-100 μ m and have an intrinsically low cost. The Taylor-wire, or microwire, process is a production method that produces the fibres directly from the melt in a single step. Developed by Taylor [4] in 1924, microwires are not fully commercially available but the manufacturing technique can be reproduced easily [4, 5]. Metal is held in a glass tube that is sealed at one end and induction coils provide the heat necessary to melt the metal. Once the metal has been melted, the sealed end of the tube is heat-softened concurrently and drawn to produce a metal filament with a glass coating. This glass coating may then be removed and the metal retained

Fig 1: (a) Wire bundle drawing [1], (b) metal shaving [1] and (c) Taylor-wire processes

A REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

Metal fibres for electrical conduction

With enormous growth in the defence, electrical and electronic industries and with electrical equipment being produced every year, there comes an increase in the need to provide shielding from external electromagnetic radiation, radio frequency interference (RFI) and lightning while preventing any emission from known sources. The best electromagnetic (EMI) interference shielders are ferrous but most metals will provide an adequate shield. However, polymers are transparent to such radiation yet are still used to house electrical components due to their low weight, cost and electrical conductivity. Therefore, in recent years, more attention is being paid to produce a polymer-based composite that incorporates the EMI shielding benefits of metals for such applications.

A number of composite compositions have been investigated already all with the aim of improving the electromagnetic shielding effectiveness (EMSE) of the material. Bigg's [6] work included both thermoset and thermoplastic polymer resins used with varying lengths of short aluminium fibres. It was found that using longer fibres resulted in an increase in electrical conduction thus lowering the volume fraction needed in the composite, keeping the original properties of the polymer much intact. Typically for this type of application however, stainless steel wires have been used with the same conclusion that an increased presence of metal fibres produces an increased degree of shielding [7-9]. Increasing the concentration of the fibres increases the probability of fibre contact within the composite, forming a conductive network and hence increasing its shielding effectiveness. Yet, at low fibre concentrations, EMSE is satisfactory over a large frequency range [9]. As Table 1 shows, steel exhibits high absorption and low reflection of EM energy resulting in low interference and high deflection of EM waves. Not shown is that steel also has a high resistance to corrosion and oxidation and does not increase in resistivity with time, nor does surface damage to the fibres decrease the shielding effectiveness. For these reasons, stainless steel is the metal of choice for EMI applications.

Materials	Conductivity	Permeability	Absorption loss*	Reflection loss ⁺
Silver	1.05	1	1.05	1.05
Copper	1.00	1	1.00	1.00
(annealed)				
Aluminium	0.61	1	0.61	0.61
Steel (SAE 430)	0.02	500	10	4×10^{-5}
Nickel	0.20	100	20	2×10^{-3}

* taken as the product of conductivity and permeability of the metal

⁺ taken as the ratio of conductivity to permeability of the metal

Table 1: Electrical properties of some shielding materials relative to copper. Adapted from Cheng *et al.* [7]

Research into knitted-fabric-reinforced composite laminates has also been undertaken in order to improve EMSE. By incorporating metal into the knitting yarn itself, a higher degree of metal wires may be present thus improving both mechanical properties and EMSE. This is the impetus behind the work of Cheng *et al.* [7]. Glass fibres were knitted together with stainless steel fibres and impregnated with a polypropylene matrix. It was found that the EMSE of this composite was affected by the concentration of the metal fibre, the thickness, or number of plies and the fabric knit structure. The added benefit of using such knitted composites over

simple fibres was that impact resistance was also markedly increased without any loss of conductivity and hence EMSE.

Another area in which metal fibres are particularly useful is in lightning strike applications. Nearby strikes generate a strong EM field while target strikes create pulsed current flow within the object or vehicle. These current flows induce voltage pulses that affect nearby circuits or components and are of much concern to both structural and electrical engineers [10]. Already various applications use stainless steel fibres that are woven together with graphite in an attempt to protect against lightning [11] although in aircraft, materials such as nickel-coated carbon and metal mesh are generally used to direct the lightning away from vulnerable areas.

Metal fibres for mechanical properties

Strength

Reinforcement of any material with metal fibres potentially serves two purposes. The first is to strengthen a material against static and dynamic loads while the second is to strengthen against impact. A number of studies have been carried out on epoxy and ceramic matrices and have found that the higher the interfacial strength between the fibres and the matrix, the higher the mechanical strength of the overall system. In a study where titanium fibres were introduced into a glass ceramic matrix, the strength was found to increase linearly with increasing fibre volume fraction, and a composite composed of 20% titanium fibres sustained stresses five times higher than the fracture stress of the matrix alone [12]. In addition, Hoffman *et al* [13] investigated and modelled the stress-extension behaviour of ductile aluminium fibres embedded in alumina matrix and found that the high constraint provided by the matrix raises peak stresses in the fibres. Higher strength resulted from this constraint which came with a little detriment to the toughness.

Studies regarding epoxy matrices involved graphite, glass and organic fibres, which all lead to the fibres failing first. However, upon the introduction of metal ribbons the failure strain at room temperature of the metal exceeds that of the epoxy and matrix failure is precedent [14]. Similarly, Huang *et al.* [15] implanted epoxy resin with twisted steel filaments of around 0.20 μm and found over 18 times increase in elastic modulus over the epoxy resin itself.

Fracture Toughness

Much work on metal fibres regarding fracture toughness has focused on ceramic matrix materials, for example as in [16,17], and it has been found that the best results can be reached by using continuous reinforcements [18]. The major mechanism of improving this toughness is through impeding fracture with the use of intact fibres. These fibres bridge the cracks thus delaying failure of the material. Figure 2 shows the crack path of a brittle composite in tension. Cracking through the matrix is favoured as opposed to along the fibre/matrix interface and ductile fibres are able to bridge the cracks and avoid early catastrophic failure. Most theories suggest that the ductile phase, acting as a crack bridger, deflects energy built up within the brittle matrix and releasing it through

Fig 2: Glass matrix with titanium fibre composite in tension [12]

plastic deformation. However, with a very restrictive and rigid matrix, this ductile deformation is inhibited by a very strong fibre/matrix interface.

Heating pre-strained titanium-nickel alloy, also known as a shape memory alloy (SMA), in the form of fibres in an epoxy matrix causes a change of phase of the alloy resulting in a compressive stress within the fibre. Shrinkage of the fibres decreases the stress concentration around any crack tip present in the vicinity of the fibre thus reducing the stress intensity factors and improving fracture resistance [19]. The use of SMAs as crack bridgers have been investigated further and modelled in [20,21], amongst others. Along similar lines, high shrinkage of the matrix material is able to grip the reinforcing fibres tighter thereby increasing the energy needed to open a crack, also resulting in increased toughness [22].

Improved fracture toughness is not restricted to such brittle composites. Stainless steel fibre/plastic matrix systems display improved fracture toughness, provided that the relatively hydrophobic steel has been surface treated, or that interfacial reactive agents are added [8].

Fibre/Matrix Interface

Performance of a composite is mainly due to the stress transfer between the fibre/matrix interface, and therefore proper wetting of the metal fibres is extremely important. Different metals, and indeed matrix materials, have different wettability properties and additives must be included into the composite system to aid adhesion. Twisted fibre cords can provide a rough surface for mechanical locking with the matrix, which provides an adhesion enhancement [15]. Various surface treatments for example chemical etching, may also be applied for additional interface interaction. The dimensions of the fibres also has a profound effect since a small aspect ratio will not allow good load transfer due to small surface areas for adhesion.

The bulk mechanical properties of the matrix also control the type of interfacial forces required for good adhesion. In the case of polymers, for example, if the interface can handle enough stress to induce deformation such as flow or yielding of the polymer, then good adhesion may be obtained. Such deformation can only be induced if the interface consists of many covalent bonds or has sufficient surface roughness for toughening [23]. Considering a ductile polymer matrix, a high interfacial shear strength suggests that shear yielding is the dominant energy dissipation mechanism. Thus improvements in properties such as flexural and impact strength can be realised [8]. A different mechanism occurs in brittle matrices where there is minimal to no shear yielding upon the application of a stress. In this case, energy dissipation occurs due to frictional sliding of the two phases at the fibre/matrix interface [13]. Too high a mechanical constraint prevents frictional sliding and debonding of the fibres leads to lower toughness yet allows for higher strength of the composite [13].

Wetherhold and Lee [22] investigated the role of shaped metallic fibres in brittle epoxy matrices in pullout tests. The ends of nickel and copper fibres were impacted and modified such that there was good anchorage in the matrix during pullout. Straight fibres debond during the initial stages of pullout and frictional sliding at the matrix interface provides the contribution to pullout work. End-impacted fibres debond in the same way but due to the anchorage, the fibre is able to plastically deform. This extra deformation energy is able to contribute to a greater toughness value without compromising on composite stiffness at low embedment depths. However, for angled embedment, it was found that frictional sliding at the fibre/matrix interface was a superior pullout mechanism and highlights the importance of surface roughness in this case, as was also studied and modelled by Bowling and Groves [24].

At increased angles, frictional sliding also occurs with anchored fibres, preventing full plastic deformation to occur and resulting in lower pullout work.

The importance of the thermal coefficient of expansion in metal fibre composites with a brittle ceramic matrix was recognised by De With and Corbijn [25]. Various metal fibres were incorporated into hydroxy-apatite, the main constituent of bone and teeth. Due to the high thermal coefficient of the ceramic, the choice of fibres that had similar thermal coefficients were limited. However of those tested, two important details came from SEM results following a three-point bend test. The first was a reaction layer that had formed at the fibre/matrix boundary. Figure 3(a) shows an example of such a reaction layer which is undesirable due to degradation of overall mechanical properties of the composite [26]. The weak boundary layer formed hindered the load transfer between the two phases. The second observation was that after introducing a fibre such as aluminium oxide, where there was an expectation that no reaction would occur at the interface, the fibres were then too brittle to avoid matrix cracking. Figure 3(b) is an example of the extent of failure within the matrix, due to large differences in thermal coefficients. Additionally, with processes such as thermal cycling, interfacial microcracks due to thermal coefficient differences accumulate at the interface resulting in weaker interfacial strength and thus degrading many of the mechanical properties of the composite [22].

Fig 3: SEM micrograph of (a) Hastalloy X fibre/hydroxy-apatite matrix and (b) Aluminium oxide fibres/hydroxy-apatite matrix [25]

Although it has been discussed that differences in thermal expansion can induce much residual stress, once a good combination of fibre and matrix has been chosen, these differences can be an advantage provided that this difference is small enough. Thermal stresses induced at the interface during cooling can induce an overall compressive stress such as is the case with titanium fibres and glass matrices [12]. This compressive stress contributes to good adhesion and hence results in good strength properties. The initial crack opening force can also be increased due to compressive stresses which must be overcome before crack opening can begin, resulting in an increase in toughness and higher failure strains [13,27].

CONCLUSION

Although continuous metal fibres introduced as a third component in composite systems have not been thoroughly examined, the potential for such materials are high. Certain mechanical properties, in particular fracture toughness, and electrical properties all improve with the addition of metal fibres. In terms of electrical properties, further examination of processes such as lightning strike protection and electromagnetic shielding is recommended based on results found from literature. Woven and knitted fabrics have only been looked at from an

electrical point of view and mechanical properties that may be gained from such materials should also be examined. A number of metal fibre types are currently available, each offering their own specific properties, for further research in producing a new family of composite materials.

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